

COOPERATION SESSION

07 February | Tuesday | 12:00-13:00 | online

[Click here to join the meeting](#)

Participants: Coordinators of the CCN projects and FOODRUS partners involved in cooperation activities

Type of event: Meeting for CCN members, organized by FOODRUS

Objectives:

- *Exchange of experiences on data sharing and stakeholders' engagement*
- *Discussion about the cooperation activities proposed (see Annex II)*

Expected outcome: Learn about other projects' experiences and strengthen a community for knowledge exchange and finding synergies among ongoing projects.

AGENDA

12:00-12:10 **Welcome words. Quick overview of CCN achievements and cooperation activities.** *Mónica de Prado, ELIKA*

12:10- 12:30 **Sharing experiences on main topics:**

Stakeholders' Engagement:

- ✓ **AGROBRIDGES**, *Eirini Efthymiadou, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL*
- ✓ **LOWINFOOD**, *Clara Cicatiello, University of Tuscia*

Data Sharing:

- ✓ **LIFE FOSTER**. *Barbara Archesso, ENAIP NET*
- ✓ **ZEROW**, *Sasa Straus & Andra Tanase. ITC-cluster & Asociatia Transilvania IT*

12:30.12:35. **Q & A to speakers** (chat)

12:35-12:55 **Open discussion** (20 min)

- ✓ *Barriers and challenges on data sharing / stakeholders' engagement*
- ✓ *Any other topic for cooperation?*

12:55-13:00 **Meeting closure.** *Ainhoa Alonso, FOODRUS coordinator*

CCN projects: <https://www.foodrus.eu/cooperation/>

MAIN OUTCOMES

Attendance: 28 participants

CCN Projects attending:

AGROBRIDGES	ESPIGOLADORS	LIFE- FOODWASTEPREV	SIRCLES
CEMIS	FAIRCHAIN	LOWINFOOD	STRENGHT2FOOD
COFRESH	FOODRUS	MODEL2BIO	VET LOVES FOOD
ECOWASTE4FOOD	LIFE FOSTER	REFRESH	ZEROW

There were invited the 35 projects of the CCN and the FOODRUS partners involved in cooperation activities.

During the previous work with the CCN members, two main topics of interest were identified for a cooperation session: **Stakeholders’ engagement & barriers in Data sharing.**

Mónica de Prado, FOODRUS Cooperation task leader, presented an overview of CCN achievements and the cooperation activities proposed for the following months: resources’ repository ([EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub](#), [Innovation Platform](#)); Participation in thematic Workshops of CCN projects (WS scheduled: FOODRUS; COFRESH); Contribution to surveys of the CCN projects; Exchange of researchers.

After FOODRUS presentation, 4 projects shared their experiences.

Stakeholders' Engagement: [AGROBRIDGES](#), [LOWINFOOD](#)

MAIN OUTCOMES OF STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101000788.

BEST PRACTICES, SOME IDEAS

- Involving replicators and actors as partners in the project: pros and cons
- “convincing” replicators and stakeholders that are not part of the consortium
- Talking “business to business”

- Household recruitment requires incentives
- Even with incentives is sometimes very challenging, especially if representativeness is sought

Data Sharing: [LIFE FOSTER](#), [ZEROW](#)

GOAL OF MONITORING

Increase the **use of raw materials and semi-finished products** and increase in the **rate of consumption / re-use of the preparations**

Achieve a FW reduction between **5.1 and 14%** (depending on the centre), **with 9.1% average value**

Minimize the incidence of food waste in VET centres

FLW Data Sharing & the 0FLW Data Space

- ZeroW will establish the 0FLW Dataspace by supporting semantic interoperability in the SILLs and supporting scaling through adoption of IDSA standards and methodologies.
- A federating catalogue of compliant data sources will be set up and managed.
- ZeroW will set up the 0FLW Dataspace, its catalogue, governance and collaborative business models, starting with and between the SILLs as well as with the existing relevant Data Spaces and data sharing initiatives and developments.
- ZeroW will also make available a Catalogue of demonstrated and 0FLW DS compliant intelligent technologies for 0FLW applications.

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14

The FOODRUS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°101000617.

After the presentations, a debate was opened to discuss about barriers and challenges on these topics or any other cooperation activity for the future. As input to this exchange of ideas, FOODRUS shared the main barriers and best practices on stakeholders’ engagement identified by the finished projects of the CCN ([CCN webinar 2022 report](#)) during the CCN webinar hold last 14 February 2022.

Stakeholders' engagement

CCN WEBINAR 2022- Report on barriers & Best practices on FLW-

Barriers	Lessons learnt/Best practices
Sometimes involved actors show a great interest but have a low compromise during the project. Opposition or negativity to cooperate between different stakeholders in the same sector are observed.	Clarifying the up-front commitment of engaged partners can help ensure a more stable commitment throughout the project duration and beyond. This is also related to the issue of “ownership of the solutions” which is an important factor when aiming for high stakeholders’ engagement. Early engagement for cooperation. Find stakeholders from previous projects with know-how on the solutions proposed.
Stakeholders’ difficulties in carrying out the technical work led by a partner or implementing the solution at real scale, above all if it is a small company.	Stakeholders’ integration and understanding of the solutions with technical partners and pilots from the beginning
Lack of common understanding and methodologies for co-creation of solutions	Having representation of each stage of the VC and maintaining communication with key stakeholders enables action and outcomes to be multiplied. It is convenient to facilitate collaboration among them and work towards a common goal
	Creating a common platform among partners/stakeholders helps to create pledges, community engagement and obtain data statistics
	The importance of volunteers as knowledge disseminators : stakeholders interested in meeting people offline through events, the ability to talk about experiences, and the ability to use the role of an ambassador.

A Google Form was created after the meeting to collect any other questions that weren’t asked during the session (see Annex I).

Ainhoa Alonso, coordinator of FOODRUS, closed the meeting explaining the current state of the project and how other projects can be informed or participate in it.

Status of the Project and next steps

ANNEX I

QUESTIONS & ANSWERS (from Google Form)

<i>Question From</i>	<i>Addressed to</i>	<i>Question (please include your question inserting a comment. Add in the first columns the name of your project)</i>	<i>Answer (your question will be redirected to the coordinator/s)</i>
FOODRUS	LIFE FOSTER		
FOODRUS	ZEROW		
AGROBRIDGES	ALL		
ZEROW	ALL		
ZEROW	ALL		
....		
...		

ANNEX II

Cooperation activities proposed to CCN members

CCN PROJECTS - activities proposals	Answer CCN Project 1	Answer CCN Project 2	Answer CCN Project 3	Answer CCN Project 4	Answer CCN Project x
Cooperation sessions					
Resources' repository					
Participation in thematic Workshops					
Contribution to surveys released by other projects					
Exchange of researchers (based on the complementarities among projects)					
OTHERS					

Cooperation sessions

1. Cooperation sessions

Main topics identified:

- 1. Barriers in data sharing:**
 - ✓ Best practices for standardisation and treatment of qualitative data
 - ✓ Development of a common data space enabling the integration of different data sources
- 2. Engagement of end-users / stakeholders:**
 - ✓ Co-creation session with end-users/stakeholders
 - ✓ Successful strategies for actors recruitment in research activities
 - ✓ How to transfer project results to end-users / stakeholders
 - ✓ Roll-out of innovations and how to ensure adoption by end users

Experience from AGROBRIDGES, LOWINFOOD, LIFE FOSTER & ZEROWASTE

Resources repository

2. Resources' repository

EU Food Losses and Waste Prevention Hub

Potential Hub as resources repository (news, events, reports, guidelines, materials)

Possibility to publish or obtain information about other initiatives

FILTER BY

Sector 0/9 ▾

Type of resource/news 0/12 ▾

Author 0/13 ▾

Target audience 0/14 ▾

Country (where the action takes place) 0/35 ▾

Choose a Tag ▾

Apply Filter **Reset Filter**

MEMBER STATES INITIATIVES

Select a member state ▾

Resources
Search our growing database of resources to discover food loss and waste prevention initiatives carried out across the EU and beyond!

SHARE YOUR KNOWLEDGE AND EXPERIENCE!
Join us and help us build a growing community striving to reduce food losses and food waste.

Benefits of becoming a member :

- ✓ Contribute to a growing library of resources
- ✓ Share your latest news
- ✓ Receive the monthly newsletter

Sign up and share

Already a member? Log in

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Resources repository

2. Resources' repository

- Inventories (searchable databases) of
- Case studies/Pilots/Living Labs, 3 projects
 - Initiatives, 100+
 - Innovations, 100+
 - Practice abstracts, 3 projects

Innovation Platform

Links to ISEKI-Food Association e-learning site

Managed by FAIRCHAIN and CO-FRESH projects. Soon to add EU4Advice

Live Twitter feed from 5 projects

Watch the video tutorial below and learn how to use the SFS Innovation Platform!

The FODRUS European Union programme

Sustainable Food System Innovation Platform

225+ registered users

The SFS Innovation Platform is an online environment for those interested in sustainable food who want to stay up-to-date (and maybe grow their activities)!!

On this Platform, individuals can publicize their initiative(s) and/or innovation(s), and EU projects can publicize their Practice Abstracts. After completing a 2-minute registration form, you can upload text and photos about your activities! While anyone can scroll or search initiative and innovation summaries only registered users can get more information including contact details of authors, and only registered users can make posts.

The Platform allows all to search publications and weblinks related to sustainable foods and to the projects that are platform contributors.

The Platform also offers a link to free online courses on topics geared towards small and mid-sized food professionals: e.g., "Best Practices in Short Food Supply Chain Innovations" and "Introduction to Intermediate Food Value Chains".

REGISTRATION

To take full advantage of the SFS Innovation Platform you can register. Registered users can add innovations, initiatives, publications and weblinks; they can rate innovations and have access to pages hidden from visitors. Registration is fast and easy, only six questions, and your profile remains private.

8

Participation in thematic Workshops

3. Participation in thematic workshops

8 open workshops planned for 2023

We will share 3rd WS soon

[EVENT REPORT – How to monitor and report food loss and food waste? - foodrus.eu](https://foodrus.eu)

[ONLINE WORKSHOP: Food upcycling and food waste recycling – what is it all about? – foodrus.eu](https://foodrus.eu)

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9

3. Participation in thematic workshops

Participation in thematic Workshops

2023 CO-FRESH WORKSHOPS

8 open multiactor workshops planned for M36-M41 (sept' 23 – feb'24)

7 Cross-Exchange visits related to Pilot Cases
(half-day, including a visit to the pilot facilities)

(Italy, France, The Netherlands, Poland, Hungary, Spain [2])

1 in Slovakia to present main projet outcomes

Topics: implementation of technologies, co-creation, practical solutions

We will share the info in the next months

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www.linkedin.com/company/co-fresh

10

Contribution to surveys released by other projects

4. Contribution to surveys

Do you have insights on food loss and food waste? Help the FOODRUS project to conduct its research activities!

The FOODRUS project is currently promoting three different surveys on food loss and waste:

- [Survey on the main causes and solutions of food waste](#)

The aim of this survey is to collect insights about (1) the causes and (2) potential solutions to prevent food loss and waste. Please [fill out this survey](#) according to your opinion/experience and let us know why food is wasted and how you think we could tackle this problem.

- [Survey on legal and economic barriers](#)

The aim of this survey is to identify the legal and economic barriers to food loss and waste prevention. The results of this survey will be used to prepare policy recommendations for national and European legislators. [Fill it out here.](#)

- [Survey on food waste prevention best practices](#)

The aim of this survey is to identify opportunities for business symbiosis and circular flows, detect food loss and waste prevention and valorization practices and collect data on food loss and waste generation. This survey is available in English, Spanish and Slovakian. [Learn more here.](#)

Submit your inputs and contribute to our work to build resilient food systems in Europe!

<https://www.foodrus.eu/participate-in-the-foodrus-surveys/>

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10

OTHERS

6. Other cooperation activities proposed

- ✓ **Circular economy:** Good working practices from different countries.
- ✓ Find solutions to the engagement of **NEET** and people at risk of social exclusion in general

- ✓ **D&C:**
 - Discuss and share solutions to increase the number of people reached by communication and dissemination activities
 - Collaboration together in publications

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